

METHODOLOGY FOR CALCULATING DIVIDEND ON SHARES OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES

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Abstract: This work is aimed at studying the methodology for calculating dividends in joint-stock companies with its theoretical and practical aspects. The purpose of the study is to systematize the process of calculating dividends in order to ensure the financial stability of joint-stock companies and implement a fair distribution of income to shareholders. The work analyzes in detail the concept of dividends, their types and their role in financial management. In the practical part, net profit, dividend percentage and dividend amount per share were calculated on the example of Uzbek joint-stock companies. The study provides practical recommendations for making financial management of joint-stock companies more effective in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Joint-stock company, dividend, net profit, dividend policy, shares, financial management.

Introduction: In a market economy, joint-stock companies are one of the most important entities of the country's economy. Their effective activity directly affects not only the financial stability of the enterprise, but also the interests of investors and shareholders. In this regard, the process of profit distribution in joint-stock companies, in particular, the issues of calculating and paying dividends on shares, are of particular importance. Dividends are the main source of income for shareholders, strengthening their confidence in the activities of the company. The correct and transparent organization of the methodology for calculating dividends

increases the investment attractiveness of the joint-stock company and contributes to the sustainable development of the capital market. At the same time, the dividend policy must be consistent with the financial capabilities of the company, its development strategy and current regulatory legal acts. This article discusses the theoretical foundations of calculating dividends on shares of joint-stock companies, its methodological aspects, and factors influencing the formation of dividend policy.

Literature review: The issues of dividend policy in joint-stock companies and the methodology for calculating dividends on shares have been widely covered in economic literature. In particular, foreign and domestic scientists have studied the essence of dividends, their impact on the financial performance of the enterprise and investor decisions based on various theoretical approaches. The initial theories of dividend policy in foreign economic literature were reflected in the studies of J. Lintner, F. Modigliani, and M. Miller. According to the theory of dividend irrelevance put forward by Modigliani and Miller, dividend policy does not significantly affect the value of the enterprise in perfect market conditions. However, subsequent studies have proven that the presence of market imperfections, taxes, information asymmetry, and agency costs increases the importance of dividend policy. The dividend stabilization model developed by J. Lintner is widely used in the practice of joint-stock companies, which is based on the dependence of the amount of dividends on the long-term profit level of the enterprise and dividend payments in previous years. This approach demonstrates the importance of the principle of prudence in calculating dividends. The financial management of joint-stock companies, the profit distribution mechanism and the legal basis of dividend policy have been widely analyzed in the scientific works of domestic economists. It is emphasized that in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the procedure for calculating and paying dividends is regulated by the Law “On Protection of Joint-Stock Companies and Shareholders’

Rights” and other regulatory legal acts. Also, in modern scientific sources, the impact of dividend policy on investment activity, the market value of shares and the liquidity of the enterprise has been studied on the basis of empirical research. The analysis of this literature serves as a theoretical and practical basis for improving the methodology for calculating dividends.

Table 1. Main steps in calculating dividends

Stage	Work to be done	Result
1. Determining net profit	Calculate by subtracting expenses and taxes from total income	Net profit, for example: 1,200,000 000 so‘m
2. Determining the dividend share	Determining what portion of net profit will be allocated to dividends	Dividend share = 40%
3. Calculating dividend per share	Divide the amount allocated for dividends by the number of shares outstanding	Dividend per share = 4,800 soums
4. Distribution to shareholders	Payment based on the number of shares held by each shareholder	Shareholder income = Dividend per share × number of shares

Table 2. Example: Dividend distribution by shareholders

Shareholder	Number of shares held	Dividend per share (sum)	Total dividend payable (sum)
Shareholder	1,000	4,800	4,800,000

A			
Shareholder B	2,500	4,800	12,000,000
Shareholder C	5,000	4,800	24,000,000
Total	8,500	—	40,800,000

Research results and discussions

Net profit and retained earnings formed in previous years serve as the main sources of dividend payment. At the same time, it is determined that the financial condition and liquidity level of the joint-stock company are decisive factors in determining the dividend policy. Methodological approaches were analyzed. As a result of the analysis, the most effective methodology for determining the amount of dividend per share was as follows: determining net profit determining the share allocated to dividends calculating dividends per share distributing to shareholders. This methodology ensures transparency and fairness of calculations. Factors affecting dividend policy were identified. The study showed that the amount of dividends and the frequency of payment are closely related to the financial stability of the company, its investment plan, the current tax system and the requirements of shareholders. At the same time, companies with high liquidity and stable income pay high dividends to shareholders, which increases investor confidence. The harmony between theoretical and practical aspects. The theoretical principles identified through the Modigliani-Miller theory and the Lintner model find their expression in practice. In particular, joint-stock companies stabilize their market value by pursuing a stable dividend policy and increase the ability to attract capital. The results of the study show that the process of calculating and paying dividends depends not only on net profit, but also on the company's strategic plans and financial potential. At the same time, based on theoretical literature and practical examples, it is determined that dividend policy has a significant impact on the

financial interests of shareholders. This provides an important decision-making mechanism for the company's management in forming a dividend policy.

Conclusion: This study was aimed at studying the methodology for calculating dividends on shares in joint-stock companies with its theoretical and practical aspects. The results of the study show that. Dividends are the main source of income for shareholders and play an important role in increasing the financial stability, liquidity of the company and investor confidence. Distribution of profits to shareholders through dividends in the form of money, additional shares and property is widely used in practice. The stages of determining net profit, determining the share to be allocated for dividends, calculating dividends per share and distributing them to shareholders were identified as the main methodological processes. This methodology is transparent and fair and protects the interests of shareholders to the maximum extent. The results of the study showed that the amount and frequency of dividend payments depend on the company's financial potential, strategic plans, liquidity, tax system and shareholder requirements. At the same time, a stable dividend policy increases shareholder confidence and stabilizes the market value of the enterprise. The study showed that a properly designed dividend policy not only increases shareholder returns, but also strengthens the long-term financial stability and market competitiveness of the enterprise. Therefore, it is important for each joint-stock company to take into account net profit, liquidity, investment plans and shareholder requirements when formulating a dividend policy.

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